

KRIYAKALPA IN THE MANAGEMENT OF NETRA ROGAS: AN AYURVEDIC PERSPECTIVE

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Article Received on 05 May 2026,
Article Revised on 25 May 2026,
Article Published on 01 June 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20470560>

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How to cite this Article: Nisha^{1*}, Dr. R. S. Unadkat². (2026). Kriyakalpa In The Management of Netra Rogas: An Ayurvedic Perspective. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(6), 1158–1170. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license

ABSTRACT

Ayurveda emphasizes the principle of “*Swasthasya Swasthyarakshanam Aturasya Vikaraprashamanam*,” meaning preservation of health and treatment of disease. Among all sense organs, the eyes are considered supreme, as stated in “*Sarvendriyanam Nayanam Pradhanam*.” *Acharya Vagbhata*,^[1] stated that the other sense organs depend on eyesight for their accuracy. Therefore, maintaining ocular health and treating eye disorders are of great importance in Ayurveda. Classical Ayurvedic texts describe several local therapeutic procedures for ophthalmic care. *Acharya Sushruta* collectively termed these procedures as *Kriyakalpa*. *Kriyakalpa* includes therapies in which medicated formulations are applied in or around the eyes to manage various ocular diseases. These

procedures are simple, effective, and widely used in Ayurvedic ophthalmology. Since vision is essential for quality of life, preserving eye health is crucial. This article briefly reviews various *Kriyakalpa* procedures and formulations used in the management of *Netra Rogas*.

KEYWORDS: Ayurveda, *Kriyakalp*, *Netra Roga*, *Panchakarm*.

INTRODUCTION

The eyes are regarded as one of the most vital sense organs in the human body, as vision plays a crucial role in acquiring knowledge, communication, perception, and intellectual growth. Without proper eyesight, an individual’s quality of life becomes significantly affected. Recognizing this importance, Ayurvedic *Acharyas* gave prime significance to ocular health and stated “*Sarvendriyanam Nayanam Pradhanam*,” meaning that the eyes are foremost among all

sensory organs. *Ayurveda* therefore emphasizes both the preservation of normal vision and the management of ocular disorders through preventive and curative approaches. To fulfill this objective, specialized ocular therapeutic procedures known as *Kriyakalpa* were developed and elaborately described in the classical texts.

The term *Kriyakalpa* is composed of two words: *Kriya*, meaning therapeutic procedure or action, and *Kalpa*, referring to the medicinal preparation or formulation used for treatment. Thus, *Kriyakalpa* denotes a group of specialized ocular therapies in which specific medicaments are applied in or around the eyes for therapeutic benefit. In *Ayurveda*, treatment (*Chikitsa*) is broadly classified into three categories: *Antahparimarjana Chikitsa* (internal purification therapies), as *Bahyaparimarjana Chikitsa*,^[2] (external therapeutic procedures), and *Shastrapranidhana* (surgical interventions). *Kriyakalpa* is classified under *Bahyaparimarjana Chikitsa* and is considered a unique and effective external therapy specifically designed for the management of *Netra Rogas* (eye diseases).

Kriyakalpa procedures are generally carried out in three sequential stages: *Purvakarma* (pre-treatment measures), *Pradhanakarma* (main therapeutic procedure), and *Paschatkarma* (post-treatment care). *Purvakarma* includes preparatory procedures such as cleansing and balancing the vitiated *Doshas* through suitable therapies. *Pradhanakarma* refers to the actual administration of the selected *Kriyakalpa* procedure according to the disease condition and *Dosha* predominance. *Paschatkarma* includes post-procedure care, dietary regulations, and precautions to enhance therapeutic efficacy and prevent complications. These therapies commonly involve the use of medicated ghee, herbal decoctions, powders, juices, or pastes applied directly or indirectly to the eyes and surrounding structures.^[3]

Acharya Sushruta described five principal types of *Kriyakalpa*.^[4]

Tarpana (retention of medicated ghee over the eyes), *Putapaka* (application of herbal extract preparations), *Seka* (therapeutic pouring of medicated liquids), *Anjana* (application of collyrium), and *Aschyotana* (instillation of medicated eye drops). Later, *Acharya Sharangdhara*^[5] added two more procedures, namely *Pindi* (application of medicated bolus over the eyes) and *Bidalaka* (application of medicated paste over the eyelids), and collectively termed these therapies as *Netra Prasadana Karma*, meaning procedures that promote and preserve ocular health.^[6]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Various references related to *Kriyakalpa* from classical Ayurvedic *Samhitas* and published literary sources were systematically collected, reviewed, and critically analyzed, and the conclusions derived from this study are presented in this article.

1 *Aschyotana* is considered the first-line therapy in many *Netra Rogas*,^[7] and is widely used in the initial management of ocular disorders. It involves instillation of medicated drops, ghee, or herbal decoctions into the open eyes from a height of about two *Angula*,^[8] ensuring uniform spread over the ocular surface. The medicine is usually retained for approximately 100 *Vakmatras* for optimal therapeutic action. It is indicated in conditions such as pain, redness, burning, watering, itching, irritation, and foreign body sensation of the eyes. Classical texts like *Sushruta Samhita*, *Ashtanga Hridaya*, and *Ashtanga Sangraha* describe its importance in cleansing ocular channels and pacifying vitiated *Doshas*. Common formulations include *Triphala Kwatha*, known for its *Chakshushya* and anti-inflammatory properties. *Stri Stanya* is used in *Raktapitta* and Vata-related ocular pain, while *Ksheera Sarpi* is beneficial in *Vatarakta* conditions. Thus, *Aschyotana* remains a simple, effective, and widely practiced Ayurvedic ocular therapy.

<i>Dosha</i>	<i>Yoga</i>
<i>Vata</i>	Decoction prepared using <i>Brihat Panchamula</i> , which includes <i>Bilva</i> (<i>Aegle marmelos</i>), <i>Agnimantha</i> (<i>Premna mucronata</i>), <i>Shyonaka</i> (<i>Oroxylum indicum</i>), <i>Patala</i> (<i>Stereospermum suaveolens</i>), <i>Gambhari</i> (<i>Gmelina arborea</i>), and <i>Brihati</i> (<i>Solanum indicum</i>), along with <i>Eranda</i> (<i>Ricinus communis</i>) and <i>Shigru</i> (<i>Moringa oleifera</i>).
<i>Vataj, Pittaj & Raktaj</i>	<i>Netrapurana</i> with juice extracted from paste of <i>Lodhra Twak</i> (<i>Symplocos racemosa</i> Roxb.) covered by the paste of <i>Nimba Patra Kalka</i> after drying and heating on fire.

The classification of *Aschyotana* based on *Dosha* predominance and associated ocular symptoms such as sensation of irritation, redness, itching, pain, watering, and burning is presented in Table 2 below, along with the corresponding dosage.^[9] It is recommended that the procedure be performed only during daytime for optimal efficacy and safety.

Table 2: *Dosha* Involvement and its Corresponding Dosage.

<i>Karma</i>	<i>Dosha</i>	Dosage	Time	Drug Properties
<i>Snehana</i>	<i>Vata</i>	10 drops	Evening	<i>Tikta, Snigdha</i>
<i>Ropana</i>	<i>Pitta</i>	12 drops	Afternoon	<i>Madhura, Sitala</i>
<i>Lekhana</i>	<i>Kapha</i>	8 drops	Morning	<i>Tikta, Ushna, Ruksha</i>

2. **Anjana:** *Anjana* is a *Kriyakalpa* in which medicated collyrium is applied to the inner surface

of the eyelid using an *Anjana Shalaka* (ophthalmic probe). The application is started from the *Kanineeka Sandhi* (inner canthus) and extended towards the *Apanga Sandhi* (outer canthus) in a smooth, uniform manner.^[10] After application, the patient is advised to gently close the eyes and move the eyeballs slowly to ensure even distribution of the medicine. It is primarily indicated for *Drishti Prasadana* (improvement of vision) and in patients who have undergone *Shodhana* therapies such as *Vamana* and *Virechana*, especially when residual *Nirama Doshas* affect the eyes. During the procedure, opening, closing, or rubbing of the eyes is contraindicated. Once the gritty sensation subsides, *Netra Prakshalana* with *Chakshushya* herbal decoctions is performed to cleanse the eyes and enhance therapeutic effect. *Anjana* is classified based on *Dosha predominance* and the appropriate time of administration, as presented in Table 3 below.^[11]

Table 3: Anjana According to Dosha and Time of Administration.

Anjana Type	Dosha	Time Period	Drug Properties
<i>Prasadana Anjana</i> or <i>Prasadanjana</i>	<i>Vata Dosha</i>	Evening	<i>Amla, Lavana Rasa Mridu Sheet</i>
<i>Ropana Anjana</i> or <i>Ropanjana</i>	<i>Pitta Dosha</i>	Night	<i>Tikta, Kashaya Rasa</i>
<i>Lekhana Anjana</i> or <i>Lekhanjana.</i>	<i>Kapha Dosha</i>	Morning	<i>Katu, Lavana, Ushna</i>

The specific time of day is mentioned due to the fact that during the night time (causes blockage of vessels) and during the day time (due to the intensity of the sunrays) the eye becomes weakened, so they suggest that *Anjana* be done both in the morning and evening. The period in the morning time should ideally be done during *Kapha Shamana Kaal* and in the evening, ideally during the *Pitta Shamana Kaal*. But according to *Acharya Susruta*, it is mentioned to perform *Anjana* in the morning for *Kapha Dosha*, in the evening for *Vata Dosha* and night time for *Pitta/Rakta Dosha*. Some of the pharmaceutical preparations of *Anjana* is weaker in efficacy than its predecessor, hence mentioned by *Acharya Sharangdhara* are *Gutikanjana*, selection of the preparation should be based on the *Rasanjana* and *Churnanjana* and these are applied to the vitiation of the respective *Dosha*. The doses of these are eyes using *Anjana Salaka*. Each succeeding preparation presented in the Table 4 below.

Table 4: Anjana Type and Dosage.

Anjana Preparation	Dose
<i>Gutikanjana</i>	<i>Tikshna: 1 Harenu</i> • <i>Madhyama: 1 ½ Harenu Mridu: 2 Harenu</i>
<i>Rasakriyanjana</i>	• <i>Uttama: 3 Vidanga Pramana</i> • <i>Madhyama: 2 Vidanga Pramana</i> <i>Hina: 1 Vidanga Pramana</i>
<i>Churnanjanana</i>	<i>Virechanika: 2 Salakas</i> <i>Mridu: 3 Salakas</i> <i>Snehaika: 4 Salakas</i>

Procedure for *Anjana* ^[12]

Initially, the appropriate medication and dosage should be selected based on the therapeutic objective. Once prepared, *Anjana* is carefully applied along the eyelid margins. The patient is then advised to gently close the eyes and perform slow eyeball movements to ensure uniform distribution of the medicine over the ocular surface, thereby enhancing therapeutic efficacy. During the procedure, actions such as opening and closing the eyes or rubbing them are strictly contraindicated. After the gritty sensation subsides, *Netra Prakshalan* is performed using a decoction of *Chakshushya Dravyas* to cleanse the eyes and complete the therapy. Important *Anjana* formulations described in Ayurvedic literature include *Candrodaya Varti*, *Karanja Varti*, *Samudraphenadi Varti*, *Danta Varti*, *Nilotpala Varti*, *Pushpa Varti*, *Rasanjana Varti*, and *Dhatryadi Varti*. In addition, several *Rasakriya* preparations are also widely used, such as *Lekhani Rasakriya*, *Darvyadi Rasakriya*, *Rasanjanadi Rasakriya*, *Guduchi Rasakriya*, *Punarnava Rasakriya*, *Babbula Rasakriya*, *Hijjala Rasakriya*, *Kataka Rasakriya*, and *Shirotpatari Rasakriya*. Other important formulations include *Atinidrahara Anjana*, *Prabodhana Anjana*, and *Lekhananjanana*, along with specialized preparations like *Krishna Sarpavasa Rasakriya*. These formulations are indicated based on specific ocular conditions and *Dosha* predominance, and are used for therapeutic as well as preventive management of eye disorders.

3. *Bidalaka*

Bidalaka involves the application of a selected medicated paste over the external surface of the closed eyelids, excluding the eyelashes^[13], for a specified duration. It is classified into three types based on the thickness of the applied paste: *Uttama* (thick), *Madhyama* (moderate), and *Hina* (thin). This procedure is particularly indicated in the acute stages of ocular disorders and is effective in relieving symptoms such as burning sensation, swelling, excessive lacrimation, redness, and pain.

Bidalak Yoga

1. A formulation prepared by triturating *Yashtimadhu* (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*), *Gairika* (Red ochre), *Saindhava Lavana*, *Daruharidra* (*Berberis aristata*), and *Svarna Makshika* (copper pyrite) with water is described as beneficial in the management of all eye disorders.
2. A paste prepared from *Maricha Churna* (*Piper nigrum*) and *Bhringaraja Swarasa* (*Eclipta alba*) is indicated in the management of *Arma* (pterygium).
3. *Bidalaka* prepared from *Manashila* (realgar), *Ela* (*Elettaria cardamomum*), *Haratala* (arsenic trisulphide), *Saindhava Lavana*, and honey is indicated in *Anjananamika* (external hordeolum). It is recommended following *Swedana* and *Bhedana* procedures to promote effective wound healing.
4. **Pindi:** Pindi is a Kriyakalpa procedure in which a medicated poultice is applied and bandaged over the eyes^[14]. It provides prolonged therapeutic action and enhances deeper absorption of the medicinal substances. This therapy is indicated in conditions such as *Netra Shotha* (inflammation), *Kandu* (itching), and *Vedana* (pain). Commonly used ingredients include *Shunthi*, *Nimba*, *Eranda Patra*, along with various medicated oils.

Table 5: Pindi Formulations According to Dosha.

The prepared medicated poultice is applied over the closed eyelids, either secured with a bandage or covered using *Doshaghna* leaves, and is retained in a tightly held position for the prescribed duration

Dosha	Yoga
<i>Vata</i>	<i>Eranda Patra Mool</i> (<i>Ricinus communis</i> L – leaves, roots)
<i>Pitta</i>	<i>Mahanimba Phala</i> (<i>Melia azedarach</i> fruit)
<i>Kapha</i>	<i>Sigru Patra</i> (leaves of <i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lam.)
<i>Kapha/Pitta</i>	<i>Nimba Patra</i> (leaves of <i>Azadirachta indica</i>) or <i>Triphala</i> [<i>Emblica officinalis</i> (<i>Amalaki</i>), <i>Terminalia bellerica</i> (<i>Bibhitaki</i>), and <i>Terminalia chebula</i> (<i>Haritaki</i>)]
<i>Rakta</i>	<i>Lodhra</i> (<i>Symplocos racemosa</i> Roxb.) and <i>Kanji</i>
<i>Netra Kandu and Sotha</i>	<i>Sunthi</i> (<i>Ginger/Zingiber officinale</i>), <i>Nimbadala</i> and <i>Saindhava Lavana</i>

5. Tarpana

Tarpana involves retaining medicated *Ghrita* (ghee) over the eyes for a prescribed duration within a protective boundary made of black gram dough.^[15] It is primarily indicated in *Vata* and *Pitta* predominant conditions such as *Timira*, *Kricchronmeelana*, *Shushkakshipaka* (dry

eye syndrome), and early-stage *Kacha* (immature cataract).

This therapy enhances ocular lubrication, nourishes the visual apparatus, and strengthens the ocular muscles and nerves. Commonly used preparations include *Mahatriphala Ghrita*, *Jeevantyadi Ghrita*, and *Triphala Ghrita*.

Tarpana should ideally be preceded by *Kaya Shodhana* procedures such as *Vamana*, *Virechana*, *Basti*, *Raktamokshana*, or *Shiro Shodhana* through *Nasya*. The procedure is preferably performed in the morning or evening in a clean environment free from dust and smoke (*Rajo-Dhooma Rahita*) and well illuminated (*Prakasha-yukta*).

The patient is made to lie in a supine position, and a dough ring prepared from *Yava* or *Masha* is carefully placed around the eyes to form a leak-proof enclosure approximately two inches in height. Medicated *Ghrita* is gently warmed in a water bath and poured into this ocular reservoir while the eyes remain closed, up to the level of the eyelashes. Thereafter, the patient is advised to slowly open and close the eyes intermittently for the prescribed duration.

Possible complications include heaviness in the eyes, blurred vision, excessive oiliness, lacrimation, itching, and stickiness due to increased secretions. After completion of the procedure, the medicated ghee is removed by creating an outlet in the dough ring, usually on the temporal side. The eyes are then cleansed using *Yava Pista*, *Ushnodaka* (lukewarm water), followed by supportive therapies such as *Shiro Virechana* and *Dhoomapana* to prevent *Kapha*-related disorders. The patient is further advised to avoid exposure to bright screens such as mobile phones and television.

Properly administered *Tarpana* results in improved tolerance to light, ocular lightness, clear vision, sound sleep, and ease of eye movements. Excess administration may lead to heaviness, oiliness, lacrimation, itching, and *Kapha* aggravation, whereas insufficient therapy may cause dryness, dirt accumulation, watering, disease exacerbation, and blurred vision.

Table 6: Aushadha Dharana Kaal for Different Conditions.

According to Site of Lesion	Time
<i>Sandhigata Roga</i>	300 <i>Matra Kaal</i>
<i>Vartamagata Roga</i>	100 <i>Matra Kaal</i>
<i>Shuklagata Roga</i>	500 <i>Matra Kaal</i>
<i>Krishnagata Roga</i>	700 <i>Matra Kaal</i>
<i>Dristigata Roga</i>	800 or 1000 <i>Matra Kaal</i>

<i>Sarvagata Roga</i>	1000 <i>Matra Kaal</i>
According to <i>Dosha</i>	Time

<i>Vataj Roga</i>	1000 <i>Matra Kaal</i> for 1 day
<i>Pittaj Roga</i>	800 <i>Matra Kaal</i> for 3 days
<i>Kaphaj Roga</i>	500 <i>Matra Kaal</i> for 5 days
In Healthy Individuals	Time
<i>Swastha</i>	500 <i>Matra Kaal</i>

6. *Putapaka*

Putapaka involves the application of medicated *Ghrita* or herbal juice (*Swarasa*), typically extracted through the *Putapaka Vidhi*,^[17] and retained over the eyes for a specified duration. The formulations used may be simple or classical in nature. The indications of *Putapaka* are similar to *Tarpana*, and it can be employed in all conditions where *Tarpana* is recommended. It is particularly useful for ocular rejuvenation and is often administered to relieve eye fatigue, especially after *Tarpana* therapy.^[18] *Putapaka* is classified into three types based on *Dosha* predominance, with specific ingredients and duration of administration, as detailed in Table 7 below.

<i>Putapaka</i> Types	<i>Dosha</i>	Ingredients Used	Duration
<i>Snehana Putapaka</i>	<i>Vataj</i> disorders	<i>Sarpi, Mamsa, Vasa, Meda, Madhura Aushadies.</i>	200 <i>Matra Kaal</i>
<i>Lekhaniya Putapaka</i>	<i>Kaphaj-Vataj</i>	<i>Jangala Desha Yakrit, Krishna Loha, Tamra, Sankha, Vidruma, Saindhava Lavana, Samudra Phena, Kasisa, Dadhi Mastu.</i>	100 <i>Matra Kaal</i>
<i>Ropaneeya Putapaka</i>	<i>Vataj-PittajRaktaj</i>	<i>Stanya, Jangala Mamsa, Madhu, Ghrita, Tikta Dravyas.</i>	300 <i>Matra Kaal</i>

7. *Seka*

In *Seka*, medicated liquid is poured as a continuous thin stream (*Sukshma Dhara*) over the closed eyes from a recommended height of approximately four *Angula*, for a duration determined by the involved *Dosha*. It is usually performed during the daytime, though in emergency conditions it may also be administered at night time.^[19]

This procedure is indicated in acute ocular conditions such as itching, excessive lacrimation, conjunctivitis, burning sensation, dryness, and photophobia. *Seka* is particularly useful in cases where *Aschyotana* does not provide adequate relief. After completion, the eyes are gently washed with lukewarm water, and the patient is advised to avoid exposure to bright screens such as mobile phones and television.

Classification

Putapaka is classified into three types based on the predominant *Dosha*. The specific ingredients used and the duration of administration vary accordingly, as detailed in Table 8 below.

<i>Dosha</i>	<i>Yoga</i>
Vata	Decoction prepared from <i>Aja Dugdha</i> (Goats milk), <i>Eranda Mool</i> (<i>Ricinus communis</i> L- roots), <i>Erand Twak</i> (<i>Ricinus communis</i> L - bark), <i>Erand Patra</i> (<i>Ricinus communis</i> L - leaves), is used <i>Sukosna Seka</i> . (<i>Ricinus communis</i> L is commonly known as Castor Oil Plant)
<i>Pitta & Abhighataja</i>	The powder prepared with equal quantities of <i>Sabara</i> (<i>Symplocos racemosa</i> Roxb.), fried <i>Madhuka</i> (<i>Madhuca longifolia</i>) with <i>Ghee</i> boiled in <i>Chaga Ksheer</i> (Goats milk) is used for <i>Seka</i> in <i>Pitta</i> and <i>Abhighataja Netra Roga</i> .
<i>Rakta</i>	The paste prepared with <i>Triphala</i> , <i>Lodhra</i> (<i>Symplocos racemosa</i> Roxb.), <i>Yasthimadhu</i> , <i>Sarkara</i> and <i>Bhadra Musta</i> mixed with cold water and filtered is effective. The paste prepared with <i>Laksha</i> (<i>Laccifer lacca</i>), <i>Madhuka</i> , <i>Manjistha</i> , <i>Lodhra</i> (<i>Symplocos racemosa</i> Roxb.), <i>Kalanusariva</i> and <i>Pundarika</i> is macerated with cold water is also effective here.
-	<i>Ghrita Bhrista Lodhra Churna</i> (<i>Symplocos racemosa</i> Roxb.) mixed with warm water and used as <i>Seka</i> pacifies pain in the eyes.

Classification

Lekhana in *Kaphaj Dosha* for 300 *Matra Kaal*. *Snehana* in *Vataj Dosha* for 400 *Matra Kaal*.

Ropana in *Pittaj & Raktaj Dosha* for 600 *Matra Kaal*.

Mode of Action

The therapeutic action of *Kriyakalpa* is fundamentally based on classical Ayurvedic principles, wherein the efficacy of the drug is governed by its *Virya* (potency) and *Vipaka* (post-digestive transformation). These inherent properties enable the medicament to exert a targeted therapeutic effect upon direct application to ocular structures. Once administered locally, the formulations establish direct contact with ocular tissues and progressively permeate the various layers of the eye. The drug then spreads through the conjunctival sac, fornices, and canthi, and may further extend via the nasolacrimal pathway to the nasal cavity and associated vascular channels, thereby facilitating both localized ocular action and systemic therapeutic influence. From a pharmacological standpoint, *Kriyakalpa* delivers ocular therapy through multiple routes, including methods.^[20]

- Topical instillation
- Periocular application
- Intraocular administration

Preparations such as drops, ointments, and gels are efficiently absorbed through the highly vascular conjunctival mucosa, which acts as a potent absorptive interface. This route allows rapid and effective drug action while overcoming systemic pharmacological barriers such as the blood–aqueous barrier, thereby ensuring focused therapeutic delivery at the site of pathology. The selection of an appropriate *Kriyakalpa* is meticulously determined by the *Vaidya* based on detailed assessment of *Dosha* imbalance and disease pathology. This ensures precise drug targeting, optimal absorption, and enhanced clinical efficacy. The Ayurvedic *Acharyas* demonstrated remarkable clinical foresight by formulating well-structured therapeutic protocols that integrate disease-specific indications, timing of administration, duration of therapy, and appropriate formulations, along with clearly defined signs of optimal, inadequate, and excessive treatment response.

Thus, *Kriyakalpa* represents a scientifically organized and deeply holistic ophthalmic therapeutic system that continues to hold strong relevance in both preventive and curative eye care in Ayurveda.

DISCUSSION

In Ayurvedic ophthalmic therapy, *Kriyakalpa* refers to the local administration of medicated formulations for the treatment of eye disorders. The primary objective of these procedures is to achieve an optimal concentration of the drug at the site of action for a specific duration, thereby eliciting a therapeutic response that alleviates or eliminates the disease. The selection of the appropriate medicament is carefully guided by the *Vaidya* based on detailed assessment of *Dosha* involvement and disease pathology, ensuring targeted and effective management.

Kriyakalpa procedures are designed to maximize local drug absorption and deliver effective relief in a precise and controlled manner. The classical *Acharyas* described these therapies in a highly systematic and comprehensive way, demonstrating remarkable clinical insight even in the absence of modern technological tools. They meticulously documented specific procedures, formulations, and indications for different ocular conditions, as well as preventive measures for maintaining eye health in healthy individuals. Furthermore, the Ayurvedic texts provide detailed guidance regarding the timing of administration, duration of therapy, and selection of formulations according to disease severity and type. They also describe the expected therapeutic outcomes along with signs of proper, inadequate, and excessive administration. This level of precision highlights the completeness of *Kriyakalpa* as a structured and holistic system of ocular care, making it an effective and time-tested approach in the management and

preservation of eye health.

CONCLUSION

In the present review article, the Ayurvedic ocular therapies known as *Kriyakalpa*, as described by ancient Acharyas, have been systematically discussed. Since the eyes are among the most vital organs of the human body, these specialized procedures are primarily aimed at the effective management of various eye disorders through well-established therapeutic approaches outlined in classical texts.

A distinctive feature of *Kriyakalpa* is the flexibility in selecting appropriate medicinal formulations based on the stage and severity of the disease, which are then administered through the most suitable procedure as per clinical requirement. This individualized and targeted approach enhances therapeutic precision and efficacy.

With the integration of modern scientific tools and research methodologies, Ayurvedic scholars have an opportunity to further explore and validate the principles of *Kriyakalpa*, thereby facilitating its wider global acceptance and application in healthcare.

Furthermore, as with all Ayurvedic therapeutic procedures, there is a need for scientific justification and better understanding of their probable mechanisms of action. Future clinical studies should aim to correlate these classical procedures with modern biomedical parameters, thereby strengthening their scientific foundation and expanding their evidence-based applicability.

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